

CST4ALL

Expected Key Project Outcomes

- Increased awareness of and support for CST technologies from key stakeholders and the general public.
- Strengthened capacities and willingness of key actors from different SET Plan sectors to implement cross-cutting, integrated, and holistic solutions to shared challenges.

Expected Key Long-term Impacts

- Accelerate the clean energy transition and realisation of the Green Deal through European technological and social leadership in cross-cutting solutions that have high economic, technical, environmental, and social performance.

MORE INFORMATION

Project Website
<https://cst4all.eu/en/>

Cordis Web Page
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101075408>

CONTACT

Consortium
contact@cst4all.eu

Coordinator
DLR e.V. German Aerospace Center
Institute of Solar Research

E-mail
peter.heller@dlr.de - daniel.benitez@dlr.de
<https://www.dlr.de/sf/en>

Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt
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Support to the Activities of the Concentrated Solar Thermal Technology Area of the SET Plan

Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) is a key enabling technology for larger holistic solutions that accelerate the clean energy transition and drive green economic growth

About

Overview

CST Delivers “Green” Heat: CST is an umbrella term that refers to any technology in which solar energy is concentrated to provide high-temperature heat. CST technologies consist of a **concentrator** and a **receiver**, where the concentrator is used to concentrate (i.e., focus) solar energy onto the receiver and thereby make the receiver hot. The receiver is specifically engineered to deliver “green” heat for some useful purpose.

Concept

CST can be understood conceptually as using a magnifying glass (i.e., the concentrator) on a sunny day to burn a papern (i.e., the hot receiver). In practice, mirrors instead of lenses are used as the concentrator to reduce costs.

Green, Dispatchable, Flexible & Valuable Heat

When combined with commercially mature Thermal Energy Storage (TES) technologies, CST technologies can cost-effectively supply heat that is green, dispatchable, and flexible, and therefore of high-value.

Applications

The “green” heat produced by CST can be used to deliver a diverse set of value-added energy products, including

- Electricity
- Industrial Process Heat
- Carbon Neutral Fuels (e.g., H₂)

About CST4ALL

Objective

CST4ALL aims to catalyze an array of hybridization and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other Renewable Energy (RE) technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

About CST4ALL

Methodology

CST4ALL will execute a set of intertwined workshops targeting both the Research and Innovation (R&I) and industrial communities to develop specific proposals at EU-level from a cross-sector perspective to foster public/private funding for R&I and to create the necessary political/regulatory framework conditions for the execution of the new CSP Implementation Plan.

European Commission

Relevant projects, initiatives, European Technology & Innovation Platform (ETIPs), and other sectors covered by the Strategic Energy Technology (SET)-Plan

CST4ALL

- Monitor Implementation Plan
- Support Implementation Working Group
- Catalyse cross-technology cooperation for
 - Research and Development
 - Industries and Markets
- Overcome Green Deal implementation challenges

CST Implementation Working Group with participation of Industry, Key Stakeholders, and National Funding Agencies

SET-Plan Steering Group